

A Note on Alcoholysis Reactions of Alkyl Sulphites

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A large number of alkyl sulphites have been synthesised by treating thionyl chloride with alcohols under different conditions¹:

Hesse and Majumdar² synthesised dimethyl and mixed methyl sulphites by passing sulphur dioxide into diazomethane in dry ether and alcohol:

Alcohol interchange technique does not appear to have been extended for the preparation of alkyl sulphites. In view of the success achieved in the synthesis of alkyl selenites³, selenates⁴ and tellurates and tetraalkoxides of tellurium⁵, by alcoholysis reactions, it was considered of interest to make a systematic and comparative study of alkyl sulphites also by similar techniques.

Reactions of normal alcohols with ethyl sulphite resulted in the formation of dialkyl sulphites while those with secondary alcohols yielded mixed sulphites only:

Tert. butanol did not appear to react with ethyl sulphite at all even after long refluxing and careful fractionation. This can be attributed to steric factors due to the smaller size of the sulphur atom. This is corroborated by the fact that even methyl sulphite was

1. Woerden, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, 63, 557.
2. Hesse and Majumdar, *Chem. Ber.*, 1960, 93, 1129.
3. Mehrotra and Mathur, *Jour. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 111.
4. Mehrotra and Mathur, *Jour. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).
5. Mehrotra and Mathur, *Jour. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 1.

found not to undergo the interchange reaction with tert. butanol and could interchange only one of its methoxy groups with isopropanol:

All the alkyl sulphites are colourless liquids soluble in benzene and are found to be monomeric in this solvent.

These findings are of interest when compared to those in the case of ethyl selenite³ in which case also only one ethoxy group was replaced with secondary and tertiary alcohols. However, methyl selenite could interchange both methoxy groups with secondary and tertiary alcohols.

EXPERIMENTAL

All glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used throughout the work, and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Fractionations were carried out as described earlier³.

All the reagents were dried in the usual manner³. Ethyl and methyl sulphites were prepared by the action of thionyl chloride with ethanol and methanol and the fractions distilling at 161° and 121.5° respectively were collected. Molecular weights were determined in refluxing benzene using a Semimicro Ebulliometer with thermister sensing. Refractive indices were measured by Abbe's Refractometer.

Sulphur was estimated by converting the sulphur content into sulphate, using alkaline potassium permanganate as the oxidising agent under refluxing conditions and precipitating as barium sulphate using barium chloride as the precipitating agent. The ethanol in the azeotrope was estimated by an oxidimetric method⁶.

(1) *Reaction between ethyl sulphite and n-propanol*: To ethyl sulphite (4.50 g) was added n-propanol (12 g) followed by the addition of benzene. The reaction was endothermic. The reaction mixture was refluxed under a column for about eight hours. Ethanol produced during the course of the reaction was slowly fractionated out azeotropically with benzene at 88°. Excess of the solvents were removed at the column and on finally drying the contents under reduced pressure a colourless liquid (4.64 g, 75%) distilling at 65°/9 mm. was obtained (from 3.0 g to 1.56 g, 52%). Found: S, 18.90%; Mol. Wt., 160; μ , 1.4016. Calc. for $\text{O}=\text{S}(\text{OPr})_2$: S, 19.28%; Mol. Wt., 166.

(2) *Preparation of methyl sulphite*: To ethyl sulphite (14.58 g) were added excess of methanol and benzene and the contents were subjected to distillation. The process was repeated until the temperature of the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of rising above 57°. Excess of the solvents were distilled out at the column (B_{14}) and the fraction distilling at 121.5° was slowly collected (6.23 g, 54%). Found: S, 28.90%; Mol. Wt., 115; μ , 1.4580. Calc. for $\text{O}=\text{S}(\text{OMe})_2$: S, 29.09%; Mol. Wt., 110.

For brevity the results of these two and other similar reactions are given in the table I.

TABLE I

S. No.	Reactants (g)	Product and State of yield	Yield		Analysis % S		Mol. Wt.		Refractive index
			Undistilled product	Distilled product	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1.	Ethyl sulphite (14.58) + Methanol (excess)	$O=S(OMe)_2$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 121.5°C.	—	6.23g 54%	28.90	29.09	115	110	1.4560
2.	Ethyl sulphite (4.50) + n-propanol (12)	$O=S(OPr^o)_2$ A colourless liquid distilled at 65°C/9mm.	4.04g 75%	3.0g 1.56g 52%	18.90	19.28	160	166	1.4016
3.	Ethyl sulphite (5.62) + n-Butanol (9)	$O=S(OBu^o)_2$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 76°C/10mm.	5.02g 100%	3.05g 2.30g 75%	16.49	16.48	200	194	1.4458
4.	Ethyl sulphite (4.32) + Isobutanol (11)	$O=S(OBu^i)_2$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 65°C/7 mm.	3.82g 94%	3.82g 3.0g 79%	16.43	16.48	199	194	1.4320
5.	Ethyl sulphite (3.23) + Isopentanol (13)	$O=S(OAm^i)_2$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 86°C/10 mm.	4.02g 77%	4.02g 3.70g 80%	14.52	14.41	229	222	1.4126
6.	Ethyl sulphite (4.15) + Isopropanol (15)	$O=S(OPr^i)(OEt)$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 55°C/7mm.	3.56g 65%	3.56g 2.75g 77%	20.96	21.05	158	152	1.4560
7.	Ethyl sulphite (6.23) + Sec. butanol (13)	$O=S(OBu^s)(OEt)$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 65°C/10 mm.	4.23g 57%	4.23g 3.20g 76%	19.19	19.28	170	166	1.4430
8.	Methyl sulphite (9.15) + Isopropanol (37)	$O=S(OPr^i)(OMe)$ A colourless liquid, distilled at 48°C/10 mm.	4.70g 54%	3.68g 2.05g 67%	22.92	23.18	144	138	1.4210

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